

NOTE

COVID-19: FOREIGN REMITTANCES AND MIGRANTS' WELL-BEING IN BANGLADESH

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic has disrupted every sphere of life and livelihoods around the world. Many migrant workers from the Global South, such as Bangladesh, working in the Gulf countries were reported to be impacted by COVID-19, but the direct voices and views of migrant workers themselves and their households are largely unknown. This research adopts a mixed-method approach to assess the impact of the pandemic on foreign remittances to Bangladesh and the well-being of migrant households. The primary data collection involved fieldwork conducted in four migrant-dense villages, situated in Mymensingh and Meherpur districts of Bangladesh. A set of 221 household surveys was administered. In addition to the surveys, 52 semi-structured interviews were carried out, engaging with key individuals at community, district, and national levels such as heads of migrant households, returnee migrants, managers of migration financiers, owners of labor recruiting agencies, officials of the district manpower office etc. Results show that although a significant number of Bangladeshi migrant workers returned home since the COVID-19 pandemic and the outflow of Bangladeshi migrant workers shrank by 69 percent in 2020, remittance inflows at the national level witnessed a growth of 18.5 percent in 2020, which did not resonate with the negative prediction made by the World Bank. However, this research found a macro-micro mismatch, indicating a substantial decline in remittances at the household level. This might be due to the existence of a robust unofficial channel for remittance sending. Approximately 62% of migrant households in the case study sites experienced a 32% reduction in remittances during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to the pre-COVID-19 period. In response to the decline in remittance income, a majority of migrant households (77%) resorted to utilizing their accumulated savings. Additionally, approximately 20% of households sought financial support and borrowing from friends, relatives, and community members. At the community level, the local economy experienced a sharp downturn, leading to a ripple effect that affected everyone within the community. To address the unofficial remittance sending, the Government of Bangladesh should implement effective measures to curb unofficial remittance channels. Upskilling initiatives have the potential to alleviate the vulnerability of Bangladeshi migrant workers, fostering increased income stability. Policymakers should place greater emphasis on crafting savings instruments tailored to the specific needs of migrant households. It is also imperative to prioritize an income diversification policy at the community level to mitigate dependence on remittances.

JEL Classifications: F24, F22 and J15

Keywords: COVID-19, remittances, Bangladesh, Gulf countries, migrant workers

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INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic has devastated health and economies across the globe. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the outbreak a Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) on 30 January 2020 (Sohrabi et al. 2020) and characterized it as a pandemic by 11 March (World Health Organization 2020). As of 16 June 2022, about 534 million people had been confirmed for the coronavirus infection across the globe, and a total of 63 million people have died so far, according to the World Health Organization situation report. The effects on lives and livelihoods are massive and continue to unfold.

The spotlight has focused in large part on the world's wealthiest countries, with little attention being placed on the impacts and implications of COVID-19 on the local and national economies of the poorer, migrant-sending countries such as Bangladesh and the communities within them.

The pandemic has negatively impacted every sphere of life, taking a heavy toll on physical and mental health, social life, education, and all sectors of the economy (Nicola et al. 2020). To 'flatten the curve', governments everywhere had instituted measures, including border closures, restrictions on movement, and measures to increase physical distancing. Lockdown measures to stop the spread of coronavirus had pushed people inside their homes, suspending or halting economic activities. Millions of migrant workers in the Gulf and other host countries languished in labor camps, having been fired or furloughed (Ullah 2020, Amnesty International 2020).

Migrant workers in foreign host countries and their family members left behind are seriously disadvantaged, given drastic falls in income and difficulty in remitting funds. Migrant workers in the Middle East had been forced to stand down from jobs, at times crammed in unsanitary labor camps, and faced high infection rates, with often no way home (Chulove 2020).

Bangladeshi migrants in the Gulf suffer health and financial risks, given their involvement in low-paid and dangerous jobs. Migrant workers in this region are often subject to 'abuse and exploitation' in the form of wage theft, forced labor, risky working conditions, and unhealthy accommodation (Ahmed et al. 2019). Migrant workers have often been denied access to available health and healthcare systems in many countries, undermining calls for Universal Health Coverage as stated in the Sustainable Development Goals (Mosca et al. 2020). The COVID-19 crisis aggravated these risks to migrant workers (Amnesty International 2020). Protecting the health and safety of migrant workers, in keeping with the SDGs 8.8 and goals around good and fair work, has been seriously disrupted. Up until the middle of 2021, the total number of deaths of Bangladeshi migrants around the world reached 2,700 among which 1,200 were in Saudi Arabia (Siddiqui 2021). Almost half of the migrant workers in Singapore infected with COVID-19 were from Bangladesh (Siddiqui 2020).

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this paper is to analyze:

- 1) trends in remittance flows and fluctuations, particularly in the context of COVID-19;
- 2) impacts of COVID-19 on Bangladeshi migrant workers and their families;
- 3) coping strategies taken by the migrant households; and
- 4) community effect of changing remittance inflows.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Immediate after the COVID-19 pandemic and lockdown in countries where Bangladeshi migrant workers work, there had been wide media coverage nationally and internationally about the sufferings, hardships, health and safety issues of Bangladeshi migrants overseas and their reintegration problems at home (Wam 2020; Pattisson 2020). Based on the newspaper reports and statistics on the returnee migrants, Karim, Islam, and Talukder (2020) put forward some policy suggestions to reintegrate the returnees in the critical juncture of the crisis. In an initiative to the early assessment, some Civil Service Organizations (CSOs) conducted rapid studies or short surveys, mainly with the returnee migrants. A short survey—conducted by 9 CSOs involved in migration and remittances—with the returnees returning from different host countries reveals that a significant percentage of workers surveyed faced health risks, mental stress, and financial stress hardships.

Financial hardships stemming from layoffs and falls in wages negatively affected the food and non-food consumption in migrant households (Siddiqui 2020). A rapid study by IOM documents that about half of the returnees experienced challenges upon returning to Bangladesh. The major challenges were finding jobs (63%), mental/psychological health issues (24%), no social support networks (24%), and repayment of debts (23%) (International Organization for Migration 2020). The same concern was echoed in a joint study in early 2021 by BRAC, UN Women Bangladesh, and the Centre on International Cooperation at New York University (UNB 2021). Indebtedness has become a serious concern in Bangladesh because of exorbitant migration costs. Often the migration costs exceed \$4,500 (3.2 times GDP per capita), which is much higher than that of other labor-sending countries (Mobarak, Sharif, and Shrestha 2020), and recouping the initial cost of migration may require as much as 15 months' work or more in some destination countries (Rahman 2015; Farole et al. 2017).

Later, several studies have explored the nature of remittances and the impact of the pandemic on the lives of migrants abroad. Chowdhury and Chakraborty (2021) shed light on the remittance flows to Bangladesh after the COVID-19 pandemic. However, this study did not look into the effects of change in remittances at the household level. In addition, it offers very limited reasoning for the unusually increasing trend of remittances to Bangladesh during the crisis. Based on Facebook posts made on different Facebook pages during the COVID-19 pandemic, Jamil and Dutta (2021) analyze the impact of COVID-19 on the lives of the migrants in the destination countries, covering the stories of job insecurities, abuses, mental stresses, and community supports. Wu and Kilby (2022) highlighted the precarity of Bangladeshi female migrants in Middle Eastern countries

during the COVID-19 pandemic. Ansar (2022) also focuses on the lives of female Bangladeshi migrant workers in destination countries and at home. They faced the burden of overwork, isolation, wage theft, economic hardships, exclusion from health services, sexual and physical abuse, deportation, and social stigma at home. However, none of the studies explored the household-level impacts: change in remittances, consumption, and coping strategies to deal with the crisis.

Moreover, earlier studies only emphasized the impacted returnee migrants who came back during the period of crisis. The impact on the households whose migrant members could not return home or the conditions of those who were not affected financially, and the coping strategy of the affected migrant households is largely unknown. Thus, this study will contribute to the body of literature comparing remittance inflows at the macro level with the flows at the micro level and showcasing the impacts of the COVID-19 crisis on migrant households and their coping strategies.

METHODS AND DATA

FIGURE 1. MAP OF THE CASE SITES

Source: *Banglapedia*

This research is informed by a case study methodology. For this research, both primary and secondary data were used. For primary data, fieldwork in four migrant prevalent villages in Mymensingh and Meherpur districts in Bangladesh was conducted in March-September 2021. A total of 221 household surveys were carried out. Along with the household surveys, 52 semi-structured interviews were conducted with the heads of migrant households, returnee migrants, and community key persons, as well as key informants at the district and national levels such as managers of migration financiers, owners of labor recruiting agency, director of district manpower office, principal of technical training center and an expert in the field of migration and remittances. Trishal

upazila (sub-district) under Mymensingh district and Mujibnagar *upazila* under Meherpur district were selected purposively for the fieldwork.

Since statistics related to migrant households at the *upazila* level are not readily available, we consulted with *upazila* statistics officer, local government representatives, and community key people to select the migrant-prevalent villages. After the consultations, Chholimpur, Golavita, and Borgaon villages under Trishal *upazila* and Dariapur village under Mujibnagar *upazila* were selected for surveys and interviews. We used the World Bank and Bangladesh Bank remittances databases for secondary data. This research got ethics approval from the University of New South Wales' Human Research Ethics Advisory (HREA) Panel.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Trends in Remittance Income in the Wake of COVID-19

World Bank statistics estimate that, in 2020, Bangladesh ranked eighth in the world and third in South Asia, with remittances of \$19.8 billion that account for 6.2 percent of GDP (The Global Knowledge Partnership on Migration and Development 2020). Bangladesh Bank statistics, since 1976, remittance flows to Bangladesh have increased by an average of 20 percent per year and have become a more significant source of foreign exchange than the inflows of foreign aid. During the 1980s, on average, remittances in Bangladesh were 2.7 percent of GDP, while foreign aid inflows were 6.5 percent of GDP. During the 2000s, however, on average, remittances were much higher (7.24 % of GDP) than that of foreign aid inflows (2.10 % of GDP), changing the pattern of foreign exchange earnings (Uddin and Murshed 2017: p. 490).

However, remittances were hit hard by COVID-19, which spread globally, including across South East Asia and the Middle East, where most Bangladeshi workers are employed. Governments suspended public gatherings and shut down workplaces to stop the spread of the virus. Work-from-home measures were widely instituted to enforce physical distancing. However, many Bangladeshi workers in the Gulf supplied physical labor as low or unskilled workers—as waiters, gardeners, cleaners, and construction workers - and physical distancing was difficult, if not impossible (Yea 2020, Ullah 2020). The fall in remittance inflows to Bangladesh was visible immediately after the lockdown measures were instituted. Comparing monthly remittance figures in 2020 and 2021 with those of 2019, it is evident that remittances to Bangladesh in January 2020 did not fall and were slightly above the figures for the same time in 2019 (2.58 % more) (Figures 2 and 3).

Although remittances in February 2020 were lower than that in January 2020, the figure was 10.20% more than that of the same time in 2019. However, from March to May, remittance flows were significantly lower than that of the same months in 2019. Remittances in March, April, and May 2020 fell by 12.50 percent, 23.80 percent, and 13.93 percent, respectively. The fall in April is similar to the projection made by the World Bank that remittances in Bangladesh would fall by 22 percent in 2020 (The Global Knowledge Partnership on Migration and Development 2020).

FIGURE 2. MONTHLY REMITTANCES, 2019-2021

Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2021

However, surprisingly, belying the predictions made by international financial institutions, remittance flows from June to December 2020 bounced back with a significant surge compared to the same months in 2019. This trend was also visible in the first quarter of 2021, with a monthly year-on-year growth rate ranging from about 20 percent (in January) to 89 percent (in April). Then afterward, the remittance flows tended to plummet, and it was at the lowest ebb of about -20 percent growth in September. We offered several plausible explanations for the remittance conundrum. First, due to the gradual reopening of economic activities and lifting of movement restrictions, workers could, at that later point, send withheld remittances back home. Second, migrant workers, especially unmarried males, do not usually send their entire earnings back as remittances (Mobarak, Sharif, and Shrestha 2020); rather, they save some portion of their income in the host country. Not only the unmarried but also some married workers do not send the whole part of their income back home. One of the returned migrants in the interview said, *'I do not send whole money back home. I send only monthly consumption amount. I keep the remaining money with me. For purchasing land and other assets, I send the bigger amount'* (IV-8, MN). Because of job losses and negative prospects of staying in host countries, the migrant workers sent their accumulated savings home. Thirdly, the government of Bangladesh has recently implemented a 2 percent cash incentive facility on remittances,

which has subsequently been increased to 2.5%, aiming to incentivize workers to utilize official channels for sending money (Bangladesh Bank 2019).

FIGURE 3: MONTHLY YEAR-ON-YEAR GROWTH RATE OF REMITTANCES, 2020, 2021

Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2021

A remittance survey in Bangladesh, reported in 2016, showed that about 22 percent of remittances are sent through unofficial channels (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics 2016). Official statistics do not record remittances sent by unofficial channels such as *Hundi* (informal money-sending channels). Switching from unofficial to official channels to remit money might have played a significant role. Since *Hundi* is an illegal way of sending money, the exact percentage of *Hundi* is hard to know. The actual percentage of *Hundi* might be much higher than the estimated percentage. In that case, changing the mode of sending money towards a formal way will have a positive impact on the official statistics of remittances. Furthermore, remittances are sometimes countercyclical; at the time of economic downturn or disasters in the home, country remittances may increase. (Frankel 2011; Yang and Choi 2007). Out of altruistic motives, migrants send more money during a tough time at home. Data shows that remittance flows to Bangladesh during natural disasters increased dramatically (Figure 4). Disasters, such as the cyclone of April 1991, cyclone ‘Sidr’ of November 2007, and Cyclone ‘Aila’ (May 2009) caused significant destruction in Bangladesh. There were also severe floods that inundated Bangladesh and caused huge financial losses in 1992, 1998, and 2004.

Remittances from the UK and the USA, where more Bangladeshi expatriates live permanently, surged in the years following these disasters. In 1991, after the major cyclone, remittances from these two countries showed positive growth from a previously negative one. In the aftermath of the countrywide flood in 2004, remittance growth also increased

for the following two years, growing by 54.3 percent in 2004-05 and 41.7 percent in 2005-06. In the financial year of 2009-10, when the devastating cyclone *Sidr* swept over Bangladesh, the growth rate experienced a remarkable surge, skyrocketing from -3.1 percent in the previous year to an impressive 23.6 percent and then slumped to a meager 1 percent in the following year (Figure 4). These trends highlight the countercyclical nature of remittances from countries where Bangladeshi expatriates have settled long-term and earn higher incomes. Along with the COVID-19 pandemic, Bangladesh also faced two other disasters: cyclone *Amphan* in May and countrywide floods in July 2020. These two disasters might have played a role in the surge of remittances. Well into 2021, the remittance ‘magic’ came to an end, and it took its predicted falling trend since a good number of migrants returned home and a good number of workers could not go overseas since the pandemic hit in 2020.

FIGURE 4. COUNTERCYCLICAL REMITTANCES FROM THE USA AND UK

Source: Bangladesh Bank, 2020

Impacts of COVID-19 on the Life and Livelihood of Migrant Workers in Bangladesh

In the initial stage of the COVID-19 pandemic, the World Bank projected that, in Bangladesh, remittances would fall by about 22 percent in 2020, dropping to \$14 billion (The Global Knowledge Partnership on Migration and Development 2020) from a previous high of 18.3 \$billion. But remittance inflows were record-high later in 2020 and 2021, belying the World Bank prediction. However, we found a macro-micro mismatch, showing that remittance inflows—immediately after the COVID-19 lockdown in the GCC countries—to migrant households decreased significantly. About two-thirds (62%) of the migrant households in the case study sites witnessed a fall in remittances by one-third (32%) during the COVID-19 pandemic as compared to the pre-COVID-19 situation (Figure 5). No single household reported receiving higher remittances compared to the pre-covid situation. Some migrant workers struggled a lot to survive in the destination country,

let alone send money back home. Whatever money they got was spent on food and accommodation. One wife of a migrant worker explained that her husband's income level

FIGURE 5. CHANGES IN REMITTANCE RECEIPTS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

Source: Household survey, 2021

was cut down by more than half, and all the salary he used to get was spent on his food and accommodation. She explained:

Before the pandemic, he [migrant husband] used to get a salary of 2,500 Saudi Ryal and also would earn some overtime payments. Now, the salary has been slashed to 1,000 Ryal with no overtime payment. This amount is finished for his food and accommodation over there (IV-1, MN).

During interviews with migrant household heads and returnee migrants, it was learned that the majority experienced income loss due to the absence of overtime working payments, constituting a significant portion of their earnings. One returnee migrant stated: *'When the lockdown was enforced, we could not go out. [...] I got the regular [basic] salary only. I could not do the overtime'* (IV-11, TR). Another respondent, the wife of a migrant worker, said that her husband did not lose his regular job, but he lost the overtime jobs from which his major share of income would come. She stated: *'He did not lose the job. But what he did outside [with other employers] in the overtime period was totally lost'* (IV-3, TR).

Some migrant workers placed in large companies did not face any fall in remittances. One wife of a migrant worker stated: *'He is not facing any problem. He is getting the same salary regularly'* (IV-9, MN). This was echoed in the response of another returnee who returned from Singapore. He noted: *'We have not faced any problem. Every week we were getting tested. We could work on maintaining social distancing. My salary was as before. My company was very good'* (IV-11, TR). Despite not experiencing any fall in income, some migrants could not send money back home due to movement restrictions

or shutdown of the money-transferring outlets. Another wife of a migrant worker working in Malaysia put it: *'He is involved in fruit picking. This work had not been disrupted. For the first three months, we did not receive any money because he could not send money to us due to the lockdown in the city* (IV-11, MN).

Workers in smaller establishments reported experiencing relatively more job cuts, slashed salaries, furlough, and wage theft. These smaller establishments were hit hard, and because of their precarious footings, they struggled to cushion the recession caused by the COVID-19 pandemic—so many of them had to shut down their businesses. One returnee migrant mentioned:

They [who were in a small company] had suffered a lot. The sufferings have no bounds. Our company was large, employing sixty thousand workers. There are many more sub [small] companies employing only 30-40 workers who have shut their businesses (IV-13, TR).

During the initial stage of COVID-19 pandemic, in an initiative to stop the spread of the virus, the local administration in Bangladesh marked the houses of the returnee migrants with a red flag so that people could single out them. However, for this activity, there was a phobia attached to the returnee migrant workers that they only brought the virus in. They were also socially stigmatized. One village leader observed:

In the initial stage of the pandemic, if a migrant returned from overseas, his home was marked with a red flag to isolate them so that people could avoid the contact. For them, there was a risk of infection in the community (IV-4, DP).

The workers who temporarily returned home faced a daunting dilemma as they grappled with the uncertainty of being able to resume their overseas work due to the mandatory double vaccine requirement imposed by the labor-receiving countries. When vaccines were available in Bangladesh, inoculation was prioritized for frontline workers such as health workers, police, public officials, and older people. In the initial stage, outgoing migrants were left out of the inoculation program. When they were inoculated, the scarcity of vaccines also prolonged their departure. One returnee migrant who came back home on leave from Saudi Arabia and was trapped stated:

I came back home on leave, and I cannot go back again. My visa is about to expire. It is a great problem. I have not gotten two doses of the vaccine. If I do not get two doses, I have to embrace quarantine of 14 days [in Saudi Arabia]' (IV-11, TR).

These households faced severe hardships since they sat idle for almost one year. In this idle time, many of them could not manage any local employment.

Coping with the Crisis

To cope with the falling remittance income, most of the migrant households (77 %) spent from their accumulated savings. And about 20 percent of households borrowed from friends, relatives, and community people (Figure 6). Because of the increased

creditworthiness, migrant households could also easily borrow from the community and relatives compared to their non-migrant counterparts.

FIGURE 6. COPING STRATEGY

Source: Household survey, 2021

Those who faced severe falls in income also reduced food and non-food consumption, as well as expenditure on some particular heads in addition to earlier strategies. As seen in Figure 7, affected households reported a significant decrease of approximately 25 percent in food and 43 percent in clothing compared to pre-COVID-19 levels. Households saw a reduction in savings by about 53 percent compared to the previous time. Most of the affected households postponed the construction and repair of houses. However, those who continued spending in this head saw a reduction of 72 percent.

Community Effect

At the community level, the local economy, especially in those rural areas with a large population of migrants, was plunged into recession, which had a knock-on effect on all in the community. For example, migrant households spend a significant amount of remittances on building and repairing houses, which positively affects employment and income in the community. Increased consumption expenditures by migrant households spill into the community at large. As we discussed earlier, most of the migrant households abandoned the construction or repair of houses, and those who continued expenditure in this head spent only one-third of the normal time. This has affected the local economy and employment. During the fieldwork, some key informants—i.e. school teachers, traders, and local government representatives—mentioned that the community businesses, especially the business of construction materials, faced great damage since most of the migrant households withdrew expenditure from the construction and repair of houses. It is found that the remittance-receiving households spend some money on poorer community people

FIGURE 7: REDUCTION IN EXPENDITURE

Source: Household survey, 2021

out of altruism or charity. During the crisis, however, these households responded less to philanthropic causes. In rural Bangladesh, some religious community institutions like mosques and madrasa receive charities and donations from migrant households since there has been a heightened social expectation that this section of the community people contributes more to this cause. These community institutions did not get sufficient contributions.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper sheds light on the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on remittance flows to Bangladesh and the well-being of the migrants and their families at home. The COVID-19 crisis has affected every sphere of life, causing unprecedented health and economic suffering. Because of the precarious nature of working and accommodation conditions in major host countries, Bangladeshi workers have suffered adverse health impacts. There has been a macro-micro mismatch regarding the remittance flows to Bangladesh. Though about half a million Bangladeshi migrant workers lost their jobs and came back home during the COVID-19 pandemic, and overseas employment shrank by 69 percent in 2020, remittance inflows increased by 18.5 percent in 2020 (Chowdhury and Chakraborty 2021).

However, we did not find any reflection of increasing remittances at the household level in the case study sites. We have tried to discuss some possible reasons for this unusual behavior of remittances, and the unofficial channel of sending remittances might have played a large part. Ullah and Haque (2020: 158) argue that money laundering is linked to remittances in African and Asian countries. Further studies are required to unearth any link between an unofficial channel of remittance transfers and money laundering from

Bangladesh, which has become a much-talked-about issue (Mortoza 2022), where the COVID-19 crisis can be a reference point.

About two-thirds of the migrant households experienced mild to severe falls in remittances, and they have used accumulated savings and reduced food and non-food consumption as coping strategies to the crisis. The decline in income and subsequent decrease in expenditure had a profound impact on local economies and the individuals who directly or indirectly relied on the households receiving remittances. These findings have the following policy implications.

The research has exposed a macro-micro mismatch of remittances, raising concerns about the prevalence of unofficial channels for remittance transmission. To address this issue, the Government of Bangladesh should implement effective measures to curb unofficial remittance channels. The susceptibility of less-skilled workers in small companies to termination or furlough during economic crises in host countries underscores the need for prioritizing upskilling initiatives. This approach aims to provide these workers with increased income stability.

Evidence suggests that migrant households exhibited resilience during economic crises by relying on accumulated savings and heightened creditworthiness. In light of this, policymakers should place greater emphasis on crafting savings instruments tailored to the specific needs of migrant households. Given the substantial dependence of economies in migrant-dense villages on remittances, any disruptions in remittance flows affect the entire community, irrespective of recipient status. Hence, there is a crucial need for policies that extend beyond individual households to address the broader community impact.

Recognizing the heavy reliance on remittances, it is imperative to prioritize an income diversification policy. Specifically, offering special incentives for investing remittances in small businesses and farming can reduce the community's overdependence on remittances, fostering economic resilience in the face of external shocks.

REFERENCES

Ahmed, MS, Das, NC, Huq, L, Prabhakar, P and Sulaiman, M 2019 *Beneficiary Vulnerability Analysis and Engagement for Bangladeshi Overseas Labour Migrants*, BRAC Institute of Governance and Development, Dhaka.

Amnesty International 2020, *COVID-19 Makes Gulf Countries' Abuse of Migrant Workers Impossible to Ignore*. Available from: <<https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/campaigns/2020/04/covid19-makes-gulf-countries-abuse-of-migrant-workers-impossible-to-ignore/>>. [30 April 2020].

Ansar, A 2022 'Bangladeshi women migrants amidst the COVID-19 pandemic: Revisiting globalisation, dependency and gendered precarity in South-South labour migration', *Global Networks*, vol.23 no.1, pp. 31-44.

Bangladesh Bank 2019 FE circular no. 31.

Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics 2016, *The Survey on Investment from Remittance 2016*, Ministry of Planning, Dhaka.

Chowdhury, MB & Chakraborty, M 2021, 'The impact of COVID-19 on the migrant workers and remittances flow to Bangladesh' *South Asian Survey*, vol. 28, no.1, pp. 38-56.

Chulove, M 2020, 'Migrant Workers Bear Brunt of Coronavirus Pandemic in Gulf', *The Guardian*, 19 April 2020. Available from <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/apr/19/migrant-workers-bear-brunt-of-coronavirus-pandemic-in-gulf?CMP=Share_iOSApp_Other>. [30 April 2020].

Farole, T, Cho, Y, Bossavie, L, & Aterido, R, 2017, 'Bangladesh Jobs Diagnostic' Jobs Series No. 9. World Bank, Washington, DC.

International Organisation for Migration 2020, *Rapid Assessment: Needs And Vulnerabilities of Internal and International Return Migrants in Bangladesh*. Dhaka.

Jamil, R & Dutta, U 2021, 'Centering the Margins: The precarity of Bangladeshi low-income migrant workers during the time of COVID-19' *American Behavioral Scientist*, vol. 65, no. 10. pp. 1384-1405.

Karim, MR, Islam, MT & Talukder, B 2020, 'COVID-19's impacts on migrant workers from Bangladesh: In search of policy intervention' *World Development*, vol. 136, pp.105-123.

Wam 2020, 'Coronavirus: UAE Reviewing Labour Relations with Countries Not Responding to Evacuation Requests' *Khaleej Times*, 14 April. Available from <<https://www.khaleejtimes.com/coronavirus-pandemic/coronavirus-uae-reviewing-labour-relations-with-countries-not-responding-to-evacuation-requests>>. [23 June 2020].

The Global Knowledge Partnership on Migration and Development 2020, *COVID-19 Crisis Through a Migration Lens*, World Bank, Washington.

Mobarak, M, Sharif, I & Shrestha, M 2020, 'Returns to Low-Skilled International Migration: Evidence from the Bangladesh-Malaysia Migration Lottery Program' Policy Research Working Paper No. 9165, World Bank, Washington.

Mortoza, G 2022, 'Will money laundering continue to haunt us?' *The Daily Star* 19 May. Available from <<https://www.thedailystar.net/views/opinion/news/will-money-laundering-continue-haunt-us-3026696>>. [15 June 2022].

Mosca, DT, Vearey, J, Orcutt, M & Zwi, AB 2020, 'Universal Health Coverage: Ensuring Migrants and Migration are Included' *Global Social Policy*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 247-253.

Nicola, M, Alsafi, Z, Sohrabi, C, Kerwan, A, Al-Jabir, A, Iosifidis, C, Agha, M & Agha, R 2020, 'The Socio-Economic Implications of the Coronavirus Pandemic (Covid-19): A Review' *International Journal of Surgery*, vol. 78. pp. 185–193.

Pattison, P 2020, 'Qatar's Migrant Workers Beg for Food as Covid-19 Infections Rise', *The Guardian*, 8 May. Available from <<https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2020/may/07/qatars-migrant-workers-beg-for-food-as-covid-19-infections-rise>>. [20 May 2020].

Rahman, MM 2015, 'Migrant Indebtedness: Bangladeshis in the GCC Countries', *International Migration*, vol. 53, no. 6, pp. 205-219.

Siddiqui, K 2021, 'Covid-19 deaths among migrant workers high in Gulf states: Study', *The Business Standard*, 12 October. Available from <<https://www.tbsnews.net/bangladesh/migration/covid-19-deaths-among-migrant-workers-high-gulf-states-study-314827>>. [3 November 2021].

Siddiqui, T 2020, *Impact of COVID-19 on Left Behind Migrant Households*, Refugee and Migratory Movement Research Unit (RMMRU), Dhaka, Bangladesh.

Sohrabi, C, Alsafi, Z, O'Neill, M, Khan, M, Kerwan, A, Al-Jabir, A, Iosifidis, C & Agha, R 2020, 'World Health Organization Declares Global Emergency: a Review of

the 2019 Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19)', *International Journal of Surgery*, vol. 76, pp. 71-76.

Uddin, MB & Murshed, SM 2017, 'International Transfers and Dutch Disease: Evidence from South Asian Countries' *Journal of the Asia Pacific Economy*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 486-509.

Ullah, A 2020, 'Like sardines': Migrant workers suffering in Kuwait's desert detention camps' *Middle East Eye*, 15 May. Available from <<https://www.middleeasteye.net/news/coronavirus-kuwait-migrant-workers-bangladesh-detention-camps>> [20 April 2021].

UNB 2021, '77% Percent Bangladeshi Returnee Migrants Struggling to Find Jobs: Study', *United News of Bangladesh*, 09 May. Available from <<https://unb.com.bd/category/Bangladesh/77-bangladeshi-returnee-migrants-struggling-to-find-jobs-study/68772>> [30 October 2021].

World Health Organization 2020), *WHO Director-General's opening remarks at the media briefing on COVID-19* -11 March, 11 March. World Health Organisation. Available from <<https://www.who.int/director-general/speeches/detail/who-director-general-s-opening-remarks-at-the-media-briefing-on-covid-19---11-march-2020>>. [20 April 2021].

Wu, J & Kilby, P 2022, 'The precarity of gender, migration, and locations: case studies from Bangladesh and Nepal', *Development in Practice*, vol 33, no. 2, pp. 145-155.

Yang, D, & Choi, H 2007, 'Are Remittances Insurance? Evidence from Rainfall Shocks in the Philippines' *The World Bank Economic Review*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 219-248.

Yea, S 2020, 'This is why Singapore's coronavirus cases are growing: a look inside the dismal living conditions of migrant workers' *The Conversation*, 30 April. Available from <<https://theconversation.com/this-is-why-singapores-coronavirus-cases-are-growing-a-look-inside-the-dismal-living-conditions-of-migrant-workers-136959>>. [10 August 2022].